

Thai Script

The Romanization and Thai Magic Tattoos

Natchanun Sanitdee

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Lecturer: Friederike Käte Evelyn Marie-Luise Lüpke, PhD

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1. Introduction

This paper aims to present an overview of Thai script with a touch on the use of tonal marks in pronunciation. Some data like the rhymes of consonant classes commonly practiced in Thai language class in the schools in Thailand are also demonstrated. The paper will present the development of Thai script and its components which comprise 44 consonants, 32 vowels, 4 tonal marks, and some other signs. The last two chapters will cover the romanization of Thai script as well as the renowned Thai magic tattoos.

2. The Development of Thai Script

Picture 1: Evolution of the Thai Script, accessed 5 October 2022,

<https://upload.wikimedia.org/wikipedia/commons/8/8c/Evolution_of_The_Thai_Alphabet.png>

The Thai script is the abugida used to write Thai, Southern Thai and many other languages spoken in Thailand... Abugida is a writing system in which the full characters represent consonants with diacritical marks for vowels; the absence of a vowel diacritic gives an implied 'a' or 'o'. Consonants are written horizontally from left to right, and vowels following a consonant in speech are written above, below, to the left or to the right of it, or a combination of those (“Thai Script,” 2022).

Abugidas include the extensive Brahmic family of scripts originated in India and spread to Southeast Asia, Bangladesh, Sri Lanka, Nepal, Bhutan, Tibet, Mongolia, and Russia (see picture 2). Today they are used in most languages of South Asia..., mainland Southeast Asia (Myanmar, Thailand, Laos, Cambodia, and Vietnam), Tibet (Tibetan), Indonesian archipelago (Javanese, Balinese, Sundanese), Philippines (Baybayin, Buhid, Hanunuo, Kulitan, and Aborlan Tagbanwa), Malaysia (Rencong, etc.) (“Abugida,” 2022).

Picture 2: Spread of Brahmic family of scripts (and Kharosthi) from India, accessed 24 October 2022, <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/File:Brahmic_script_travel_from_India.png>

Chommaithong, Choopakha, and Phatsrak explained the creation process of the Thai script on the website (<https://www.lib.ru.ac.th/pk/thaifont2.html>) they created as a university project as follow:

The Thai script derived from Khom script, which is a version of a south Indian script called Grantha script. The Khom script is still widely used in Thailand to write Pali and Sanskrit in a religious context. When the Khom script was first adopted by King Ramkhamhaeng the Great in 1283, his motive was that Thai language should have more consonants and tonal marks and also be quicker to write. Consequently, he added 10 more consonants in addition to the original Khom script. At the present time, each set of the added consonants have the same phoneme;

however, it was assumed that they used to have a different phoneme at the time of invention like in Pali language.

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THE THAI SCRIPT

CONSONANTS

	Mid	Mid	High	High	Low	Low	Low	Low
ก	ก	ข	ค	ค	ง	ง	จ	จ
k	k	kh	kh	kh	kh	kh	ng	ng
จ	จ	ช	ช	ซ	ซ	ญ	ญ	ย
c	c	ch	ch	s	s	ch	y	y
ด	ด	ต	ต	น	น	น	น	น
d	d	t	t	th	th	th	n	n
ด	ด	ต	ต	น	น	น	น	น
d	d	t	t	th	th	th	n	n
ป	ป	ฟ	ฟ	พ	พ	ม	ม	ม
b	p	ph	f	ph	f	ph	m	m

The sixth group in Devanāgarī, comprising the semi-vowels, and the spirants, is represented in Thai as follows:

(a) the semi-vowels (all low class consonants):

ย	ร	ล	ว
y	r	l	w

(b) the spirants (all high class consonants):

ซ	ส	ศ
s	s	s

(c) the mixed group ห (high), ฟ l (low), อ ? (middle), ฮ h (low).

NUMERALS

๑	๒	๓	๔	๕	๖	๗	๘	๙	๑๐
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10

Picture 3: The Redundancy of Thai Consonants (Campbell and Christopher, 2012)

That is why Campbell and Christopher (2012) said that the degree of redundancy in Thai script is high, with five graphs for /kh/ (the gray rectangle in picture 3), six for /th/ (the orange rectangle in picture 3), and four for /s/ (the purple rectangles in picture 3), etymologically explicable but no longer phonologically justifiable.

កា ka ក	ខា kha ខ	កា ga ក	កា gha ក	នា na ន
ចា ca ច	ចា cha ច	ចា ja ច	ចា jha ច	នា ña ន
ចា ja ច	ចា jha ច	ចា da ច	ចា dha ច	នា na ន
តា ta ត	តា tha ត	តា da ត	តា dha ត	នា na ន
បា pa ប	បា pha ប	បា ba ប	បា bha ប	មា ma ម
យា ya យ	រា ra រ	លា la ល	វា va វ	សា sa ស
សា sa ស	សា sa ស	ហា ha ហ	លា la ល	អា a អ

Picture 4: The Current Khmer Script (left), accessed 5 October 2022, <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Khom_Thai_script> and the Early Thai Script invented in 1283 called Lai Sue Thai (right), accessed 5 October 2022, <<https://www.lib.ru.ac.th/pk/thaifont2.html>>

At the time that King Ramkhamhaeng the Great added 10 more consonants to the Old Khom script to create Lai Sue Thai, it can be assumed that he was inspired by Pallawa script. The rectangles in the same color in the picture 4 signify that it comes from the same character, and the black circles are the characters that were added. From the picture 1, it can be seen that the Angkorian Khmer script, the one that King Ramkhamhaeng used to create Lai Sue Thai, does not have the character ឃ (the third to last character in mint color in the picture 1 and the character in the dotted red rectangle in picture 4). The ឃ character was obtained directly from Pallawa script.

3. Components

3.1. Consonants

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THE THAI SCRIPT

CONSONANTS

Mid		High		Low			
Mid	Mid	High	High	Low	Low	Low	Low
	ก k	ข kh	ฃ kh	ค kh	ฅ kh	ฉ kh	ช ng
	จ c	ฉ ch		ซ ch	ฌ s	ญ ch	ย y
ฎ d	ฏ t	ฐ th		ฑ th		ฒ th	ณ n
ด d	ต t	ถ th		ท th		ธ th	น n
บ b	ป p	ผ ph	ฝ f	พ ph	ฟ f	ภ ph	ม m

The sixth group in Devanāgarī, comprising the semi-vowels, and the spirants, is represented in Thai as follows:

(a) the semi-vowels (all low class consonants):

ย	ร	ล	ว
y	r	l	w

(b) the spirants (all high class consonants):

ศ	ษ	ส
s	s	s

(c) the mixed group ห h (high), ฟ l (low), อ ? (middle), ฮ h (low).

NUMERALS

๑	๒	๓	๔	๕	๖	๗	๘	๙	๑๐
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10

Picture 5: Thai Consonants and Numbers (Campbell and Christopher, 2012)

Thai consonants are divided into three classes: high (the yellow rectangle in picture 5), middle (the green rectangle in picture 5) and low (the blue rectangle in picture 5). The class of the initial consonant is one factor in determining the tone of a word or syllable (Smyth, 2014). Thai consonants are all pronounced with an inherent ‘-or’ sound (Smyth, 2003). For example, the consonants ก and ข will be pronounced /kɔː/ and /kʰɔː/ respectively. Each Thai consonant also has a ‘name’ (Smyth, 2003). For example, ก is known as /kɔː/ nuː/ where /kɔː/ is the pronunciation of the consonant, and /nuː/ meaning rat is the name. ข is known as /kʰɔː/ maː/ where /kʰɔː/ is the pronunciation of the consonant, and /maː/ meaning horse is the name.

There are 2 sets of numbers used in Thai script (the pink rectangle in picture 5): Thai number (in the first row in picture 5) and Arabic number (on the second row in picture 5).

3.2. Consonants by Class

Low class:	น	ม	ง	ร	ล	ย	ว		
	n	m	ng	r	l	y	w		
	ค	ช	ซ	ท	พ	ฟ			
	k	ch	s	t	p	f			
	ก	ฏ	ภ	ญ	ณ				
	k	t	p	y	n				
	ฉ	ท	ฒ	ฬ	ฮ				
	ch	t	t	l	h				
Mid class:	ก	จ	ด	ต	บ	ป	อ	ฎ	ฏ
	g	j	d	dt	b	bp	zero	d	dt
High class:	ข	ฃ	ถ	ผ	ฝ	ศ	ษ	ส	ห
	k	ch	t	p	f	s			h

Picture 6: The Three Classes of Thai Consonants (Smyth, 2014)

There are some tips that help Thai learners to memorize the class of the consonants more easily. The easiest way to do this is to memorize the shorter lists of mid-class and high-class consonants so that everything not on those lists can be assumed to be low-class (Smyth, 2014).

There is a rhyme for mid-class and high-class consonants as follows.

Mid-class Rhyme

ไก่ /kai/ จิก /teik/ เด็ก /dek/ ตาย /ta:i/ บน /bon/ ปาก /pak/ โอง /ʔo:ŋ/
 a chicken pecked at a child dying on the edge of the jar

High-class Rhyme

ไข่ /kʰai/ ของ /kʰɔ:ŋ/ หั้น /tɕʰan/ ถูก /tʰu:k/ เผา /pʰaw/ เสีย /sia/ หาย /ha:i/
 an egg of mine was burned devastatingly

3.3. Vowels

Picture 7: Thai Vowels, accessed 1 October 2022, <<https://sites.google.com/site/phasathiyaru2559/bth-thi-1/1-2>>

Picture 8: Thai Monophthong IPA, accessed 1 October 2022, <[https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Thai_vowel_chart_\(monophthongs\).png](https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Thai_vowel_chart_(monophthongs).png)>

Thai vowels have seven collinear symbols: ๑, ๒, ๓, ๔, ๕, ๖, ๗, five superscripts: ๘, ๙, ๑๐, ๑๑, ๑๒, and two subscripts: ๑๓, ๑๔ combined with each other and the consonants ๑, ๒, ๓ to generate the vowel systems (Campbell and Christopher, 2012). Monophthongs and diphthongs, both short and long, make 32 vowel sounds in total.

Thai monophthongs are pronounced according to the rectangles in the same color in picture 7 and 8.

3.4. Tones

Picture 9: Thai Tonal Marks

Thai is considered to be the first script in the world that invented tone markers to indicate distinctive tones, which are lacking in the Mon-Khmer (Austroasiatic languages) and Indo-Aryan languages from which its script is derived (“Thai script,” 2022).

When consonants are combined with vowels into a word, each word makes 5 different tones. However, there are only 4 tonal marks visible: ‘, ˆ, ˆ, ˆ, which are put in a second layer of diacritics. The 4 tonal marks represent a low, falling, high, and rising tone respectively with no mark for a middle tone (picture 9).

As previously mentioned, Thai consonants are divided into 3 classes: low, middle, and high. Each class of the consonants yields a different tonal shift when combined with a tonal mark. In other words, Coulmas (2003) explained that tones are continuous events connected with one another. Neither tone-class letters nor tone diacritics add an isolated feature of tone, but mark contour changes. For example, the letter ก is a low class character. When it is combined with a falling tonal mark ˆ like in the word ก้า /k^ha:/, the tone of the whole word becomes a high tone. On the other hand, the letter ข is a high class character. When combined with the same falling tonal mark ˆ like in the word ข้า /p^ha:/, it gives a falling tone.

It is also worth noting that each class of characters can only be presented and meaningful in certain tones. To help complete the pronunciation in all 5 tones, either the letter ข has to be added or it needs to change to another character with the same phoneme in a different class. To illustrate, the low class characters like ก /k^h/ are only allowed to match with the middle -, low ‘, and falling ˆ tonal marks as in กา คำ ก้า. To complete all tones, another character with the same phoneme in a different class is needed. In this case, it is ข /k^h/ in high class character group, and the complete pronunciation of all tones are represented as กา ข้า คำ ก้า ข้า. Another example is the letter ย /j/, a low class consonant. Like ก /k^h/, it

can only be presented together with the middle -, low ' , and falling ˊ tonal marks. Therefore, to complete the pronunciation of all tones, the letter ห /h/ comes into play as in ยา หยา ยา ย้า หยา. Speaking of a meaning, the latter example can be taken as evidence that only some of the tones are meaningful.

- ยา = medicine (n.)
- หยา = divorce (v.)
- ย่า = grandmother (n.)
- ย้า = no meaning by itself but in a word like โคมไฟระย้า, it means chandelier (n.)
- หยา = no meaning by itself but in a word like สังขยา (without the letter ห but pronounced the same), it means egg custard (n.)

3.5. Other Signs

Picture 10: Other Signs

Other signs used in the Thai script include:

- ๗ marks repetition of a syllable like มาก๗ /ma:kma:k/ meaning “a lot”.
- ˊ marks its bearer consonant as mute like นีรันดร์ /niran/ without the ˊ mark the word is นีรันดร /nirandɔ:n/ with the final syllable pronounced. Both words mean “eternally”.
- ๗ marks abbreviation like มหา๗ลัย /maha:lai/ which is a short term for มหาวิทยาลัย /maha:witt^hajalai/ meaning “university”.
- ๘ shortens the vowel sounds of ɪ /e:/ and u /ɛ:/. It has to always be followed by a consonant. For example, the long vowels in the words เป็๘น /pen/ meaning “to be” and แ๘็ง /k^hɛŋ/ meaning “hard” become short vowels because of the presence of the ๘ sign.

Coulmas (2003) explained the main character of the Thai writing system that “as in all Brāhmī-derived scripts, the functional unit of Thai writing is the graphic syllable consisting of a consonant base with various diacritics grouped around it”.

4. The Romanization of Thai Script

Numerous attempts to romanize Thai were made during the nineteenth century (Frankfurter, 1906, as cited in Arousseau, 1941), and the phonetic systems of the Roman Catholic and American Missions were successful, though they lacked the precision required for the rendering of personal and geographical names (Arousseau, 1941, p.154).

The systems of “The Romanization of Thai” (2022) include transcription and transliteration, and the most seen transcription system in public space is the Royal Thai General System of Transcription or RTGS. The Royal Institute issued a book in 1982 called Romanization Guide for Thai Script to set standards of the system with the explanation as follows:

The Royal Thai Institute has created two standard systems for transcription of Thai characters into Roman letters — the Precise System and the General System.

In the General System the sound of words is indicated by Roman letters only and without any diacritical markings. The Royal Thai Government has adopted the General System for use in transcribing geographical names within Thailand. The General System was chosen for romanizing geographical names on maps and in lists because it is more practical cartographically and typographically.

The Precise System indicates the tones and the pronounced letters thus showing the derivation of the words. In the Precise System there is a Roman equivalent for every Thai consonant and this system employs critical marks, many of them being tonal marks (p.1-2).

Arousseau (1941) explained more details about the general and the precise systems that:

The general system “is to be applied in case it is desired to facilitate pronunciation by foreigners, without intention of indicating the unpronounced letters or tones.” and uses no signs not carried on a typewriter equipped with the commoner diacritical marks. The precise system “is to be applied in case it is intended to indicate the unpronounced letters with a view of showing the derivation of the words and their tones” and uses no signs which would strain the typographical resources of a good newspaper. In short, it seems that Thai words may now be

satisfactorily transcribed into Roman characters, either as they are spoken or as they are written. Some time must pass before the effect of the new system on the writing of geographical names becomes apparent, but we may expect to see the results of precise transliteration on official maps. and those of genetal transliteration in the newspaper. (p.155)

In short, it is found in the Journal of the Siam Society (1941) that The Royal Institute deems it expedient to standardize the transcription of Thai characters into Roman by having a general system and a precise system, following the characteristics of the Thai language in that the general system constitutes a transcription of words as they are read, and the precise system constitutes a transcription of words as they are written.

The general system and precise system of phonetic transcription of Thai characters into Roman will be demonstrated in the sections 4.1. and 4.2. respectively.

4.1. The General System

4.1.1. Vowels

อะ อั อ่า	a
อ่า	am
อิ อี้	i
อี อัย	u
อุ อู	u
เอะ เอ็ เอ	e
แอะ แอ	æ
โอะ อ() โอ	o
เอาะ ออ	ɔ
เออะ เอ็ เออ	œ
เอ็ยะ เอ็ย	ia
เอ็อะ เอ็อ	ura
อัวะ อัว	ua
ไอะ ไอ อัย ไอย อาย	ai
เอา อาว	ao
อุย	ui
โอย	oi

ออย	ɔi
เอย	œi
เอ็อย	urai
อวย	uai
อิว	iu
เอ็ว เหว	eo
แหว	æo
เอ็ยว	ieo
ฤ (when pronounced /ru/) ฤ๓ ru	
ฤ (when pronounced /ri/) ฤ๓ ri	
ฤ (when pronounced /rœ/) ฤ๓ rœ	
ล ฤ๓	lu

Note: In typing u' may be used for u

4.1.2. Consonants

	Initial	Final
ก	k	k
ข ข ค ค ฆ	kh	kh
ง	ng	ng
จ	čh	t
ฉ ช ฌ	ch	t
ญ	y	n
ด ฎ ท	d	t
ต ฏ	t	t
ถ ฐ ท ฑ ฒ	th	t
น ฌ	n	n
บ	b	p
ป	p	p
ผ พ ภ	ph	p
ฝ ฟ	f	p
ม	m	m
ย	y	-

ร	r	n
ล ฟ	l	n
ว	w	-
ซ ทร ศ ษ ส	s	t
ห ฮ	h	-

Note: In typing ĉh may be used for čh

4.1.3. Transcription of Words

Each syllable is to be separately transcribed in accordance with the characteristics of the Thai language.

Examples

กษัตริย์	kasat
ประกาศ	prakat
ราชบุรี	Ratburi

The hyphen is to be used where in the case of its omission, the word may be read in another way.

Examples

สิ่ง	sa-ing
ปากสัตว์	pak-lat

4.2. The Precise System

4.2.1. Vowels

อะ อั อา	ăḥ	ă	a
อ่า	ăṃ		
อิ อี		ĩ	i
อึ อื		ĩ́	ur
อุ อู		ũ	u
เอะ เอ็ เอ	ěḥ	ě	e
แอะ แอ	æḥ		æ
โอะ อ() โอ	ōḥ	ō	o
เอาะ ออ	õḥ		o
เออะ เอ็ เออ	œḥ	œ (with umlaut)	œ
เอ็ยะ เอ็ย (a) final	ĩăḥ	ia	

	(b) before consonant		ie			
เอื้อะ เอื้อ	(a) final	ü'ǎḥ	ura			
	(b) before consonant		urœ			
อัวะ อัว	(a) final	ü'ǎḥ	ua			
	(b) before consonant		uo			
ไอ ไอ อัย ไอย อาย		ǎi	ǎi	ǎy	ǎiy	ai
เอา อาว		ǎo	ao			
อุย		ui				
โอย		oi				
ออย		ɔi				
เอย		œi				
เอื้อย		urœi				
อวย		uoi				
อิว		iu				
เอื้อว เอว		ěo	eo			
แอว		æo				
เอื้อยว		ieo				
ฤ (when pronounced /rʉ/) ฤ		rǎ	rʉ			
ฤ (when pronounced /ri/) ฤ		rǎ				
ฤ (when pronounced /rœ/) ฤ		rœ				
ร ฤ		ɭu	ɭu			

4.2.2. Consonants

	Initial	Final	
ก	k	k	
ข	kh	k (kh)	
ฃ	kh	k (kh)	
ค	k ^c	k(k ^c)	
ฅ	k ^c	k(k ^c)	
ฆ	kh ^c	k (kh ^c)	
ง	ng	ng	
จ	č	t(č)	
ฉ	ch	t(ch)	
ช	c ^c	t(c ^c)	

ฌ	ch ^c	t(ch ^c)
ญ	y	n
ด	d	t
ฎ	ḍ	t(ḍ)
ต	ḏ	t(ḏ)
ต	t	t
ฏ	ṭ	t(ṭ)
ถ	th	t
ฐ	ṭh	t(ṭh)
ท	t ^c	t(t ^c)
ท	ṭ ^c	t(ṭ ^c)
ธ	th ^c	t(th ^c)
ฒ	ṭh ^c	t(ṭh ^c)
น	n	n
ณ	ṇ	ṇ
บ	b	p
ป	p	p
ผ	ph	p
พ	p ^c	p(p ^c)
ภ	ph ^c	p(ph ^c)
ฝ	f	p(f)
ฟ	f	p(f)
ม	m	m
ย	y	-
ร	r	n(r)
รร	-	n(rr)
ล	l	n(l)
ฬ	ḷ	n(ḷ)
ว	w	-
ช	ç	t(ç)
ชร	ç	t(ç)
ศ	s	t(s)
ษ	ṣ	t(ṣ)

ส		s	t(s)
ท		h	-
ฮ		h	-

4.2.3. Tones

Tone notation shall be according to the sound tones, as follows:

ก	กั	กึ	กึ๊	ก๋
kḥ	kḥ̄	kḥ̇	kḥ̈́	kḥ̌

4.2.4. Transliteration of Words

Each syllable is to be separately transliterated in accordance with the characteristics of the Thai language. Add dormant final consonants or unpronounced letters in brackets.

Examples

กษัตริย์	kăṣāt(triy)
ประกาศ	prăkat(s')
ราชบุรี	Rat(ch)bŭri

The hyphen is to be used where in the case of its omission, the word may be read in another way.

Examples

สิ่ง	să-ĭng
ปากลัด	păk-lăt

5. Thai Magic Tattoos

5.1. Origin and Meaning

Picture 11: Ajarn Oh Using a Bamboo Spike to Tattoo a Yant for Seduction and Confidence (Drouyer, 2013)

Yantra tattooing or Sak Yant (สักยันต์ in Thai) is a form of tattooing using Indian yantra designs. It consists of sacred geometrical, animal and deity designs accompanied by Pali phrases that are said to offer power, protection, fortune, charisma and other benefits for the bearer. (“Yantra tattooing,” 2022)

Drouyer (2013) explained the root of the word tattoo as follows:

The word ‘tattoo’ derives from the Polynesian term ‘tatoua’ which means ‘to mark the skin’. Combining the word ‘ta’, which signifies etching into the skin, and ‘atoua’, which means the mind. In Thailand and Cambodia, the Yant is often transcribed in Khom, the ancient Khmer alphabet. In Laos, it may be written in Dhamm and in Myanmar, in Shan or in Burmese scripts. Yantra is a Sanskrit word derived from the root ‘yam’ meaning to control or restrain, or from the root ‘man’ which can be translated as ‘instrument of thought’. The Yantra, or Yant in Thai and Khmer, is a geometric design which serves as a physical support for the sacred sequences of syllables, the mantra (p.13)

5.2. Yant Reading

Picture 12: Magic Spells Written in Khom Script. Courtesy of Ajarn Kob (Drouyer, 2013)

In 2017, Chananya Techajaksemar or View, a Thai Youtuber posted a video in her channel Point of View about Yant reading. It was the term paper she wrote in her Khmer language class. She explained that Yant, due to the spatial constraint, is an abbreviated form of Pali language written in Khom script. The abbreviation is from the mantras in Pali language or *គាណ* /k^ha:t^ha:/ commonly known among Thai monks as well as Thai people. In her video, she presented a reading for 3 Yants, namely Yant Mahaut, Yant Kao-yot, and Yant Ha-thaeo, as follow:

5.2.1. Yant Mahaut

Yant Mahaut (ยันต์มหาอุตม์) helps with invulnerability and compassion.

Picture 13: Yant Mahaut, accessed 7 October 2022,

<https://1.bp.blogspot.com/_LUaWICdsG18/TPnoJwMczMI/AAAAAAAAABE/5gvvyEMG67Y/s1600/m164950.gif>

On the Yant Mahaut, it is written “นโม พุทธาย อี สวา สุ”

- นโม /namo:/ means humility.
- พุทธาย /p^hutt^ha:ja/ means the Buddha.
- อี /i/ is an abbreviated form from the first line of Ittipiso mantra praising the Buddha.
- สวา /sawa:/ is an abbreviated form from the second line of Ittipiso mantra praising the Dharma or the Buddhist principles.
- สุ /su/ is an abbreviated form from the last line of Ittipiso mantra praising the Sangha or Buddhist monks.

Therefore, the meaning of the Yant Mahaut is “I bow to the Buddha and praise the Buddha, Dharma and Sangha.”

5.2.2. Yant Kao-yot

Yant Kao-yot (ยันต์เก้ายอด) or nine spires Yant helps with protection typically tattooed on the center top of the back in various sizes and levels of complexity.

Picture 14: Yant Kao-yot, accessed 7 October 2022, <<https://i.ytimg.com/vi/FO1XMmnJ2M/maxresdefault.jpg>>

On the Yant Kao-yot, it is written “อสีวิสุ โลปุสพุก สวิทาปุยกยบ นโมพุทฺธาย มออุ อรหํฯ”. The meaning can be divided into smaller parts as follow:

- อสีวิสุ โลปุสพุก /ʔasaŋwisu lo:pusap^hup^ha/: Each syllable comes from the Ittipiso mantra spreading from the beginning till the end.
- สวิทาปุยกยบ /saŋwit^ha:pukkayapa/: Each syllable represents the first syllable of seven Abhidhamma scriptures.
- นโมพุทฺธาย /namo:p^hutt^ha:ja/ means I bow to the Buddha.
- ม /ma/ comes from the first syllable of the verse /manutsa:nanp^hutt^ho:p^hak^hawa:ti/ representing the Buddha.
- อ /ʔa/ comes from the first syllable of the verse /ʔaka:liko:ʔehipassiko:/ meaning “standing through time” referring to the Buddhist principles which remain true eternally.
- อุ /ʔu/ comes from the first syllable of the verse /ʔute^hupatipanno: sa:wakasaŋk^ho:/ referring to the Buddhist monks.
- อรหํฯ /ʔarahañ/ comes from the full verse /ʔarahañ samma: samp^hutt^ho: p^hak^hawa:/ meaning “The Lord, the perfectly enlightened and blessed one” referring to the Buddha.

Therefore, the overall meaning of Yant Kao-yot is “I bow to the Buddha. I remember the seven Abhidhamma scriptures, and I praise the Buddha, the Buddhist principles, and the Buddhist monks.”

5.2.3. Yant Ha-thaeo

Yant Ha-thaeo (ยันต์ห้าแถว) or five rows Yant is typically tattooed on the back left shoulder. It represents the blessing for success and good luck.

Picture 15: Yant Ha-thaeo, accessed 7 October 2022,

<<https://encrypted-tbn0.gstatic.com/images?q=tbn:ANd9GcT-TIzFLIAUxNDdLjIsZPiAY6blwG7zRtxAYQ&usqp=CAU>>

Picture 16: Yant Ha-thaeo On the Left Shoulder,(Drouyer, 2013)

Although there are 5 lines, they are all the same sentence just swapping the characters (“Point of View,” 2017). That sentence is written “นโม พุทธायนเมติ” /namo: p^hutt^ha:yaname:ti/ meaning “May the humility be with the Buddha” according to the literal translation, though a lot of people believe that นโม พุทธाय /namo: p^hutt^ha:ya/ means the five Buddhas.

References

- Abugida. (2022, October 9). In Wikipedia. [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Abugida#Indic_\(Brahmic\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Abugida#Indic_(Brahmic)).
- Anonymous. (1941). "Notification of the Royal Institute concerning the Transcription of Thai Characters into the Roman" (PDF). Journal of the Siam Society. Siam Heritage Trust. JSS Vol. 33.1 (digital). Retrieved September 30, 2013.
- Anonymous. (1982). Romanization Guide for Thai Script. Repr. Bangkok: Royal Institute.
- Arousseau. (1941). Official Romanization of Thai (Siamese). The Geographical Journal, 98(3), 154–155. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1787601>.
- Brahmic Scripts. (2022, October 20). In Wikipedia. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Brahmic_scripts.
- Campbell, George, and Christopher. (2012). The Routledge Handbook of Scripts and Alphabets. 2nd ed. Milton Park, Abingdon, Oxon: Routledge.
- Chommaithong, Choopakha, and Phatrsak. (n.d.). กำหนดแบบอักษรไทย. <https://www.lib.ru.ac.th/pk/thaifont2.html>.
- Coulmas. (2003). Writing Systems : an Introduction to Their Linguistic Analysis. Cambridge, U.K.: Cambridge University Press.
- Drouyer. (2013). Thai magic tattoos : the art and influence of Sak Yant. Bangkok: River Books.
- Point of View. (2017, September 9). ถอดรหัส 'ยันต์' เขียนว่าอะไร? | Point of View [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=uML8OE1RxPw>.
- Romanization of Thai. (2022, September 25). In Wikipedia. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Romanization_of_Thai.
- Smyth. (2014). Thai : an essential grammar. 2nd ed. Milton Park, Abingdon, Oxon: Routledge.
- Smyth. (2003). Thai / David Smyth. London: Hodder & Stoughton.
- Thai Script. (2022, October 17). In Wikipedia. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Thai_script.
- Yantra tattooing. (2022, October 7), In Wikipedia. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Yantra_tattooing.